

Detecting phase transitions in community structures using big data analysis of the engineering education research landscape: a European perspective

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INTRODUCTION AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

A fundamental problem facing the field of engineering education is to understand how educational research and pedagogical innovations may propagate. It is an even greater challenge to understand if any of the educational results transform into innovations – thus leading to better products and services. Recent studies have demonstrated that an effective approach to understanding the origin and flow of research innovations through complex systems is by the use of bibliometric and scientometric analyses – both of which can involve using tremendous volumes of data. Such a big data study has not been undertaken from a European perspective up to now nor has there been a clear definition of the topographic characteristics of the corresponding European and more

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global collaboration networks. Secondly, there has been no attempt to use a sequence of time segmentations to understand if there has been a notable phase transition in the European literature. As a first step to applying big data analysis to the European engineering education research landscape, our paper examines the topographic characteristics of the collaboration network found in the literature generated within the European space.

One of the most powerful mathematical tools available to engineers to study the propagation of knowledge and potentially disruptive artefacts is through the use of graphs. The network of engineering education researchers in our study is composed of researchers (represented as nodes on a graph) and the products they co-produce (represented as edges). Additionally, we represent key concepts as nodes and show how they connect to other ideas using edges. The central idea behind the use of topics as nodes is to highlight the importance of key topical areas that emerge in the body of literature. Papers represented as links just highlight connections among topics. In totality all researchers and their scientific products (papers, conference proceedings, citations, and secondary citations) are a large network exhibiting a certain level of randomness. According to Achlioptas [1], “Networks in which the formation of connections is governed by a random process often undergo a percolation transition, wherein around a critical point, the addition of a small number of connections causes a sizeable fraction of the network to suddenly become linked together” (p. 1453). This phenomenon is known as “explosive percolation” [2] of random networks. An example of such an explosive percolating event was seen in the papers published by the Journal of Engineering Education from a big-data analysis carried out by Xian and Madhavan [3]. These investigators suggested that the formation of the first 2 departments of engineering education in the US or the colloquies which eventually yielded the research agenda for engineering education in 2006 may have triggered this process.

While the general methods for conducting such studies have been well established in the engineering education literature, the goal of understanding major phase transitions begins with characterizing the topography of the knowledge space itself. In this study, using an aggregated sample of 3,331 papers published in two European-published journals, the International Journal of Engineering Education (IJEE) and the European Journal of Engineering Education (EJEE), from years 1993 to 2015 we attempt to develop some basic understanding of the topology of the engineering education literature from a European perspective. The mechanisms we use in this study are significantly different from previous studies because we rely heavily on cloud-based services that allow a larger community of engineering education to gain access to methods demonstrated in this paper. Using a variety of mathematical techniques, the goal of this research, in the long term, is to identify potentially disruptive ideas that could fundamentally transform the scientific space.

1 REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

Over the last decade there has been a growing interest in the evolution of engineering education research (EER) and a variety of approaches have been adopted to study this process. Froyd and Lohman [4] used criteria for defining the field of science education

research [5] to point out that while engineering education has been seen as an area of interest for educators since the end of the 19th century, over the last two decades there have been significant indicators of a transition to an interdisciplinary, more scholarly field of scientific inquiry into engineering education. Borrego and Bernhard [6] have compared Northern and Central European approaches to EER with those of the U.S. using a framework from the European *didaktik* tradition, which focuses on answering the w-questions of education. Borrego and Olds [7] employed an analysis of National Science Foundation funded projects as a way of characterizing development in EER in the US while van Hattum-Janssen et al. [8] followed the Froyd & Lohman [4] approach and used the Fensham criteria to track the emergence of EER in Portugal.

The approaches described in the preceding paragraph could be broadly classified as scientometric in that they measure and analyse the development of a scientific field of inquiry. In parallel with these approaches there have been a number of studies which apply forms of bibliometric analysis, a study of scientific publications, as a way of tracking the evolution of EER in different parts of the world. Wankat [9][10] analysed 10 years of JEE papers (1993-2002, 597 papers) and reported that “although a reasonable number of papers cite an educational theory or learning style, such as Kolb or the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI), less than 20 percent of the papers actually used a theory to design or analyse the curriculum, learning or teaching.” Osorio and Osorio [11] performed content analysis on publications in JEE and EJEE over the years 1998 to 2000 and observed that the first authors of JEE articles are mostly from the USA whereas authors of EJEE articles are primarily from several European countries. An analysis of empirical research in leading EER journals up to 2008 by Jesiek et al. [12] showed that the majority of published authors in the analysed articles came from the US (36%) with the EU and Australia providing 29% and 23% respectively and the level of international co-authorship was relatively low at 8%. Although we might assume that in the intervening years this trend might have diminished due to increased globalization, we note that a recently published list of the most collaborative co-authors in EER [13] contains only US scholars.

Williams and Neto [14] analysed research processes in a set of papers in IEEE Transactions on Education and ASEE-published Advances in Engineering Education in 2011, and found that in over 70% of the papers some theoretical construct, i.e., theory, model, framework or instrument was used. Malmi et al. [15] analysed 62 EER track papers from the SEFI conferences of 2010 and 2011 and identified shortcomings in the way research was reported. Wankat et al. [16] by sampling journal articles in both EJEE and JEE at 10 year intervals over a 40-year period noted that there was a gradual progression from opinion essays, reports and descriptive articles to research articles. Williams et al. [17] carried out citation analysis of 169 articles published in seven EER journals in 2011 and concluded that there was evidence of the existence of disciplinary silos and to a lesser extent geographical silos. A recent citation analysis [18] to study the global spread of EER examined 4321 publications comprising ASEE and SEFI conference papers and EJEE and JEE articles confirmed the earlier findings of Osorio and Osorio [11] in concluding that in citation terms European EER is relatively global but that in the US it is not.

It is important to note that all of the bibliometric studies described in the previous paragraphs were human curated which being quite manpower-intensive does limit the sample size that is normally studied. However, the dramatic increases in computer processing power in recent years have permitted the development of increasingly sophisticated big-data analysis procedures which have led to the emergence of machine-curated bibliometric analysis that by its nature has the potential to allow investigators to view a rather broader picture given that very large data-sets can be analysed.

The Froyd-Lohman [4] study mentioned earlier, for example, includes network diagrams produced by machine-curated analysis of extremely large data sets prepared by Madhavan et al. [19] [20]. The original studies [19] [20] describe the application of data mining techniques to study 35,591 documents from 21 different publications including Journal of Engineering Education, International Journal of Engineering Education, Frontiers in Education, ASEE conference proceedings, and IEEE Transactions on Education. This allowed the researchers to build up sophisticated researcher network profiles and characterize the interactions between scholars and groups of scholars. In a more recent example, analysis of 24,172 papers in engineering education research journals and conference proceedings over the period 2000-2011. Xian and Madhavan [3], for example, found that in-state collaboration within the US is significantly more frequent than between-state collaboration which suggests that geographical location can strongly influence how scholars form collaborations.

Big data analysis brings a further potential benefit in that not only can we identify general evolutionary trends in a field of inquiry but it can also allow us to see how educational research and pedagogical innovation propagate within and between communities of educational scholars and practitioners. Thus it can provide a means of addressing one of the fundamental problems facing the field of engineering education: understanding innovation propagation. In other words, if we are able to monitor how educational results transform into innovation, this can in turn lead to better products and services. Advances in computing power now provide us with the wherewithal to understand the origin and flow of research innovations through complex systems by applying bibliometric and scientometric analyses to very large volumes of data.

Apart from the complex data-processing procedures required for such studies there are two other challenges which arise. Firstly, given the comparative newness of the techniques and the large volumes of data to be analysed it can be difficult to initially identify emerging patterns. Secondly, once such patterns have been identified there is the question of choosing the medium in which they are best presented. It can be problematic to represent complex changing data patterns within the constraints of traditional papers such as this one and this is why some researchers have opted to complement their publications with video presentations as this medium permits more dynamic visual presentation of data. See for example the video representation that describes changes in the IEEE Frontiers in Education conference publications produced by the Interactive Knowledge Networks for Engineering Education Research [21].

2 KEY TERMS USED IN THE STUDY

Before we present the methods and analyses for this paper, we discuss a few key social network analyses terms used in this paper. The measures we use in this paper are associated with graph theory. They are known as centrality measures and allow us to answer questions about the importance and value of each node and edge (line that connects two nodes) in a network graph [22] [23]. More importantly, they provide us a means to describe the topography of the resulting graphs. The fundamental mathematical derivations and formulae are not discussed and are outside the scope of this paper. Please note that the descriptions provided below are deemed sufficient for the purposes of this paper (not necessarily exhaustive or complete).

Nodes: Authors and co-authors are represented as nodes in the first set of network graphs presented in the paper (Figs 2 – 5) while keyphrases are presented as nodes in subsequent ones (Figs 6 and 7).

Edges: The relationship between two nodes is shown as an edge i.e. a line connecting nodes. All of our graphs are directed but are unweighted (meaning thickness of the edges are not computed based on any set of factors).

Graph Density: Measures the completeness of the graph. If all authors (or co-authors) are connected with no connection gaps, then the graph density is 1. In terms of propagation of information, graphs with high density are presumed to have more pathways for information flow to occur.

Largest Connected Components/Clusters: Largest number of nodes connected together by at least one edge. This is an important topological property of graphs. Essentially, connected components show how certain groups could pick up specific types of innovations (due to an existent pathway or edge), whereas other groups (or disconnected components) may not know about these innovations.

Average Path Length: The average of all the path lengths needed to connect any two authors/concepts in a graph. When two authors are directly connected, the path length between them is 1. As the average path length of a graph increases, this essentially means that information has to flow more steps to travel from one person to any other random person (if a pathway exists).

Average Closeness: The average of all the shortest distances between one author and all other authors in the network is called closeness. In other words, this value characterizes the average of the so-called reach or potential to influence of one person in the network.

Average Degree: The average number of links emanating from or connecting to any given author in the network. Although, our graphs are directed, we did not compute in-degree or out-degree. The higher the degree, that particular author is considered more influential as more connections can be made through or pass through that person.

Average Betweenness: The average betweenness value indicates how many times on an average a single author/concept acts as a bridge or is on the shortest pathway between two authors or concepts.

Average Eigencentrality: The average index of how influential a single author/keyphrase is within the entire network. As this index increases, it is indicative that individual researchers have more power within the network to propagate their ideas as they have higher average influence. Connecting to an author or researcher with high eigencentrality would be another way for propagating newer ideas.

Average Eccentricity: The average longest geodesic distance between any two authors in the network is given the eccentricity centrality. As this value increases significantly, it is indicative that information has to travel a larger number of steps in order to reach the farthest author.

Figure 1 Overall big data work-flow showing data analyses and graph generation processes used in this study.

3 METHODOLOGY

The authors adopted a quantitative exploratory methodology to seek patterns and connections within data relating to the authors and topics studied in 3,331 articles published in the two journals EJEE and IJEE. A brief technical account of the specific procedures applied is set out below.

Figure 1 shows the overall methodology and work-flow used in this study. Our approach is significantly different from previous big data studies of network topologies in engineering education research because of our reliance on cloud-based services for much of our data processing needs. The methodological innovation here is the creation of a work-flow that is accessible to non-experts in data mining.

This study utilizes two major data sources – namely, 2,303 journal articles published in IJEE from 1997 – 2015 and 1,028 journal articles published in EJEE published from 1993 – 2014. In step 1, we collect all journal articles in PDF form from the web and deposit all of the PDFs into a file server. These files are then passed through an extraction process using a PDF Miner (Python) seen in step 2. All extracted texts are placed into a mySQL (PyMySQL) data store. This new data store is the primary data processing staging area. The next stage of the process uses Thomson Reuters cloud-based service OpenCalais (<http://www.opencalais.com/opencalais-api/>). In step 3, the extracted text is sent to OpenCalais for extracting all necessary metadata. These metadata along with appropriate tags for each paper are sent back to the mySQL data store (step 4). Immediately following this our work-flow engine initiates Gephi (step 5) followed by a one-time start of the Master Streamer via Gephi Graph Streaming (<https://marketplace.gephi.org/plugin/graph-streaming/>) shown in step 6. The process then calls for each year of the data sequentially (in step 7) using the GephiStreamer (<https://pypi.python.org/pypi/GephiStreamer/2.0.3>). The nodes and graphs are constructed using a process that enforces the required layouts indicated in step 8 – which in turn is a complete sub-process of its own shown in figure 2.

Fig 2. Process (step 8) for creating the graphs presented in this paper.

Step a in figure 2 shows the graph initially being output in some random layout that lacks any form or understandability. In step 8.b we apply a force-directed layout (ForceAtlas2) as outlined in Jacomy et al. [24]. Step 8.c applies the Lin-Log forces (ForceAtlas2) that was elaborated by Noack [25]. While step 8.d adjusts the node sizes to be proportional to the computed degree centrality, the final step 8.e is used simply for adjusting the labels to their appropriate positions. Please note that the point of figure 2 is not to be readable, but rather to show decreasing clutter and increasing clarity of the resultant graphs.

4 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Fig 3. State of the engineering education research network from a European perspective in year 1997.

Fig 4. The intermediary year 2000 shown here is significantly different with regard to connections between nodes as compared with the first year few of our analyses as evidenced in table 1.

Please note graphs are shown purely for topological descriptions. They are not designed for reading each node label or graph entity.

Based on the methods we described in the previous section, we developed highly detailed graphs for each year for which we had data from both journals – for years 1997 – 2014. Since this essentially constitutes 18 detailed graphs, in order to showcase our results, we present only a few selected ones. Figure 3 shows the network of engineering education from a European perspective as it existed in the year 1997, while

figure 4 shows an intermediary state of evolution in year 2000. We selected this year for the interesting properties that the topology of the graph displays for that year. We will discuss these characteristics next. Figure 5 shows the evolution of the field at the end of 2014.

Fig 5. Topology of the graph in year 2014 - the final year that we included in our analyses. We note many more nodes and a higher degree of connection between them

In order to discuss the topology of the network the resulted from the analyses of 3,331 EJEE and IJEE papers combined, it is important to consider Table 1, which lists the most important factors that are needed to discuss the engineering education community as seen from the European perspective.

It is very clear from the data presented in Table 1, as well as the figure 3 -5 that the engineering education community publishing in these two journals has grown significantly. Starting with just 912 authors in 1997 with 4.066 connections, the community has grown to 15,577 authors with a staggering 114,398 connections. This growth has essentially increased the average eccentricity from 1.83 in 1997 to 7.74 in 2014 – meaning, the longest geodesic distance between any two random authors on the network has increased significantly over the past years. This in combination with a phenomenal increase in average path length (1.97 in 1997 to 5.315 in 2014) suggests that there are likely to be significant bottlenecks affecting information propagation across the network.

It is notable that our analyses indicate that there is still a significant amount of community building that needs to take place to connect various parts of the European and international EER community. The graph density of a fully connected network is 1. However, in our case the graph density decreased from 0.01 in 1997 to relatively stable 0.001 (from 2007 to 2014). This indicates that there is currently a significant potential to connect and grow within this network. Given the growth of the network over the years of our analyses, the effect or ability of the individual within the larger context of the community remains particularly low. This may be a significant bottleneck to achieving major advances within the international community. Another way to look at this would be to assume a need for more leadership (and leadership development) within the larger European and international communities.

Table 1. Centrality indices computed for all the EJEE+IJEE papers from 1997 - 2014

	Authors (Nodes)	Connections (Edges)	Graph Density	Connected components	Avg. Path length	Avg. Closeness	Avg. Degree	Avg. Betweenness	Avg. Eccentricity	Avg. Eigencentrality
1997	912	4066	0.01	191	1.975	0.73	9.91	9.2	1.83	0.11
1998	1396	6637	0.007	260	3.13	0.65	9.5	51.15	2.66	0.11
1999	1791	8285	0.005	317	3.194	0.64	9.25	57.11	2.75	0.1
2000	2163	9385	0.004	367	6.791	0.6	8.67	516.9	4.81	0.09
2001	2815	13547	0.003	423	5.911	0.57	9.62	918.2	4.76	0.04
2002	3472	17651	0.003	472	6.426	0.55	10.16	1733.2	6.03	0.03
2003	4368	25475	0.003	533	5.905	0.54	11.66	2211.2	6.42	0.03
2004	5105	29232	0.002	580	5.787	0.51	11.4	3022.97	6.33	0.03
2005	5938	33615	0.002	646	5.939	0.5	11.32	3784.6	6.52	0.02
2006	7204	45101	0.002	687	5.743	0.48	12.52	5290.3	6.94	0.02
2007	8212	50499	0.001	780	5.549	0.49	12.29	5600.7	6.22	0.02
2008	9263	60241	0.001	785	5.466	0.45	13	7311.5	6.63	0.02
2009	9797	63315	0.001	794	5.575	0.44	12.92	8311.7	6.8	0.02
2010	10931	72371	0.001	837	5.576	0.43	13.24	10173.8	7.23	0.02
2011	12009	82754	0.001	867	5.519	0.42	13.78	11685.7	7.46	0.02
2012	13112	94393	0.001	891	5.365	0.41	14.3	13116.5	7.6	0.01
2013	14214	102040	0.001	911	5.319	0.4	14.35	14066.4	7.56	0.01
2014	15577	114398	0.001	926	5.315	0.39	14.68	16916	7.74	0.01

4.1 Potential for Phase Transitions

In Table 1, we highlighted 2000 as a year of particular interest. Table 1 provides some key insights that may indicate the need for further analyses that include more data from the European perspective. The average path length jumped from 3.194 in 1999 to a remarkably high 6.791 for the year 2000 while at the same time, the number of nodes and the edges connecting them did not have a particularly large jump that might explain this change. Also of almost equal importance is the fact that the average betweenness index changed from 57.11 in 1997 to 516.9 in 2000 – this is an order of magnitude jump in network terms. Furthermore, what is curious about these values is that after 2000 the average path length has been extremely steady (decreasing trend) and betweenness has been fairly steady positive trend. This would indicate that the larger community experienced some significant topological bump or disturbance in the year 2000. Our goal in this paper has been to examine the data for evidence of such interesting phenomena (perhaps analogous to the explosive percolation noted by Xian and Madhavan [3] as was mentioned in the Introduction section of this paper). However, we readily acknowledge that we need to investigate community events, literature, and knowledge products further in order to qualitatively define and confirm the significance of the year 2000 to the European and international engineering education community.

4.2 Connecting Topics

In addition to undertaking topological analyses of the collaboration networks, we also conducted detailed analyses of topical connections. Using the tags that were generated for each of the papers, we developed for the European Journal of Engineering Education and the International Journal of Engineering Education a network graph with key topical areas as nodes and papers that have common topics as edges. Here we provide the topical graphs for EJEE and IJEE for the year 2000.

Fig 7. IJEE – Topical connections in the year 2000

It is clear from figures 6 and 7 that while technology seems to be a topic of general interest in the European and international contexts, the two data sources are significantly different in their foci and cover a range of different topics. This in many ways shows that our analyses included data sources that offer data coverage. On the other hand, the graphs also show that the knowledge products have a very broad scope and included a tremendous range of ideas even in the year 2000. By 2014, the number and range of topics has grown significantly. Perhaps, this is indicative of a lack of focus within these knowledge products on any specific topic. Alternatively, this would be a strong indicator that while the community has a wide range of topical interests (and is vibrant in this regard), there are no big aggregating ideas that are emerging in the engineering education research space as seen from EJEE and IJEE perspective over the past several years. This very breadth could complicate the dissemination and propagation of any major innovations.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND LIMITATIONS

This study is perhaps the first of its kind study within the European and international engineering education domains. We have demonstrated using innovative big data mining and network visualization techniques that the engineering education space in the European context has grown significantly from 1997 to 2014. Our topological analyses suggest an increasing likelihood of information bottlenecks that would hinder information flow and the propagation of innovation. Furthermore, we have also identified the year 2000 as being of particular interest for future analyses. The topical maps show that the European community is broad and diverse – but may lack a particular focus or may need to focus on some key big ideas to promote propagation.

In terms of limitations, we understand that our findings are based on only two major data sources. While we believe that our work has tremendous analytic power, we also would like to add more data to our analyses. In the big data regime, the workflow we present based on 3,331 papers was extremely computer and time intensive to converge. Future research aims to conduct analyses that we anticipate will provide a more detailed and nuanced picture of the evolution of engineering education research in the European context.

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